

ARCOS Establishment Project Governance

Prepared by the ARCOS establishment steering group: Steve Quenette (Monash University), Paul Coddington (ARDC), Mark Gray (Pawsey Supercomputing Centre), Steven Manos (BioCommons), Ryan Fraser (AARNET), Andrew White (ARDC)

2020-08-17
v1.0

Introduction

Kubernetes is the emerging open source standard for deploying and managing scalable and portable container-based cloud-native applications. In order to realise an Australian research container orchestration service (ARCOS) and derive the full benefit of this infrastructure, an effective governance model needs to be created in order to coordinate and oversee the activities to establish the service and provide a strong focal point for development in support of this initiative. This will ensure the service is developed in an efficient manner, using a standardised approach following best practices, while engaging effectively and widely with stakeholders.

Steering Committee

The Steering Committee will be the governing body of the project to develop the ARCOS and will provide strategic leadership and governance oversight. The Steering Committee will have the delegated authority to make decisions that are in accord with the objectives, approach and scope of the project including decisions on activities, project plans and standards. The Steering Committee is expected to make key decisions based on consultations with the implementing partners and stakeholders that are represented by the members of the Steering Committee.

Scope

The Steering Committee will be tasked with providing advice and governance only during the period of the project to establish the service. Once the service has been established the current Steering Committee will be dissolved and a separate body, yet to be determined, will be responsible for the governance of the established service. This does not preclude members of the current Steering Committee from being members of the new governance body.

Membership

The Steering Committee will be composed of representatives from the main stakeholders including Digital Data and eResearch Platforms (DDeRP) organisations, institutions, Nectar

Research Cloud Nodes, NCRIS capabilities and other major users of the technology that are providing national services (e.g. Platforms). From time to time observer representatives of international best practice will be invited to sit on the Committee e.g. Cloud Native Computing Foundation (CNCF).

The chair will be elected from among the Steering Committee members. The SC is expected to meet monthly but no less than quarterly. The ARDC will provide secretariat services to the Steering Committee.

Members may resign from the Steering Committee at any time by providing notice to the Chair and other Steering Committee members.

The following preliminary membership list below is a draft and will be refined once the chair is confirmed.

Institutions Represented	Representative
Institutions and Nectar Research Cloud Nodes	Steve Quenette (interim chair)
AARNet / CAUDIT	Ryan Fraser
ARDC	Paul Coddington
HPC centres (NCI, Pawsey, MASSIVE)	Mark Gray
NCRIS capabilities Platforms and Virtual Labs	Steven Manos
CNCF (observer)	Cheryl Hung

Kubernetes Working Group

A broader group of interested stakeholders will be engaged to provide input and feedback on the project activities.

Function

The primary functions of the Kubernetes Working Group are to:

- Provide assistance and input to define and develop the project and service and associated documentation, including requirements, specifications, project plans and standards.
- Advocate for the service objectives and outcomes within their respective communities

- Advise on improving implementation and use of the services
- Deployment and support of standardised services by infrastructure providers

Membership

The Kubernetes Working Group will be composed of interested representatives from the wider set of community stakeholders including:

- Digital Data and eResearch Platforms (DDeRP) organisations,
- Institutions,
- Nectar Research Cloud Nodes,
- NCRIS capabilities,
- Other major users of the technology providing national services (eg Platforms).